

On the study of Szeged Index and Wiener Index for monocyclic graphs from geodesic topological matrices[†]

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A method for computation of szeged index (S_z) for monocyclic graphs consisting of n vertices, n even (≥ 4), has been proposed by using geodesic path-defined distance matrices D_e . A general mathematical formula is also derived for computation of S_z for monocyclic graphs of n vertices, n even (≥ 4) and the most frequently used graph theoretical invariant, the Wiener index (W), is computed from the Szeged index.

Application of graph theory in chemistry is well known. In chemical graph theory the distance properties of molecular graphs form an important topic. Quite a good number of topological indices^{1,2}, as mathematical invariants, are used in molecular chemistry to study the various properties of molecules. Wiener index³ (W) is one of the most frequently studied topological indices which is based on distances between the vertices of a graph. W has been used to explain the variation in boiling points, molar volumes, refractive indices, heats of formation, atomisation, isomerisation, vaporisation of crystal lattices of various kind of molecules. Szeged index^{4,5} (S_z) is a new topological index based on distances between the vertices of a molecular graphs. It is an extension of Wiener index on cyclic graphs. There is no established relation between W and S_z , only it is known that for a cyclic graph G , $S_z(G)$ exceeds $W(G)$ incase of cyclic molecules and $S_z(G) = W(G)$ if and only if all blocks of G are completed. Khadikar *et al.*⁶ studied monocyclic molecules consisting of n vertices, n (even) ≥ 4 . For $n = 8$ and $n = 12$ by symmetric partitions ($n/2$) (diagrametically) W and S_z had been calculated in their work and for other values of n the indices had also been reported.

In earlier attempts, distance matrices used to be considered. It would be shown in this paper that one can dispense with distance matrices. Here, S_z is calculated for monocyclic graphs of vertices $n = 4, 6, 8$ and 12 using geodesic path defined matrices, D_e , and then W is calculated using the relation,

$$W = \frac{1}{2} S_z$$

which has been derived by Khadikar *et al.*⁶.

Methodology

In an undirected connected cycle, containing graph between any two vertices, there is at least one path containing them. If more than one path connect a given pair of vertices (v_i, v_j), we denote the k -th path by symbol $p_k(v_i, v_j)$. The shortest path joining the vertices v_i and v_j is called 'geodesic', and its lengths is the topological distance $d(v_i, v_j)$. The array which collects the lengths of the path is called the distance matrix⁷⁻¹², denoted by D_e .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thus, } D_e &= N_e, d(v_i, v_j) \text{ is a geodesic, if } i \neq j \\ &= 0, \text{ if } i = j \end{aligned}$$

where, $N_e, d(v_i, v_j)$ is the number of edges on the shortest path $d(v_i, v_j)$

The subscript e , in the shortest path $d(v_i, v_j)$, of the above matrix implies that the elements are edge-defined, that is, their entries reckon edges on the path $d(v_i, v_j)$.

In acyclic structures, the Wiener (global) index is defined as

$$W = W(G) = \sum N_i, (i, j) N_j, (i, j) \quad (1)$$

where, $N_i, (i, j)$ and $N_j, (i, j)$ denote the number of vertices lying on the two sides of the edge $(i, j) \in E(G)$, $E(G)$ being the set of edges in a connected graph, G . The summation runs over all edges in G . The product $N_i, (i, j) N_j, (i, j)$ represents the contribution of edge (i, j) to the global index, W . The Szeged index, S_z , is defined according to eq. (1), but quantities $N_i, (i, j)$ and $N_j, (i, j)$ are defined as below so that definition of eq. (1) remains valid both in acyclic and cycle containing graphs.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

$$N_i(i, j) = |\{v : v \in V(G); (i, j) \in E(G), D_{iv} < D_{jv}\}|$$

$$N_j(i, j) = |\{v : v \in V(G); (i, j) \in E(G), D_{jv} < D_{iv}\}|$$

where, $V(G)$ denotes the set of vertices in graph G and D_{iv} , D_{jv} are the topological distances, i.e. the number of edges joining vertices i and j on the shortest path (i, j) . Thus, each of $N_i(i, j)$ and $N_j(i, j)$ represents the cardinality of the sets of vertices i and to j , respectively. Edge defined Szeged index, can be calculated by summing up all the edges contain in a graph,

$$S_z = S_z(G) = \sum_{\text{all}(i,j) \in E(G)} N_i(i, j)N_j(i, j)$$

S_z and W for monocyclic graphs G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_4 (Fig. 1) containing vertices $n = 4, n = 6, n = 8$ and $n = 12$, are calculated by forming distance matrices D_e for them. For

Fig. 1. (G_1) Monocyclic graph of vertices $n = 4$; (G_2), monocyclic graph of vertices $n = 6$; (G_3), monocyclic graph of vertices $n = 8$; (G_4), monocyclic graph of vertices $n = 12$.

graphs G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_4 , the distance matrices are defined as in Tables 1–4. S_z is calculated from D_e by summing the entries columnwise.

Table 1. Distance matrix for $n = 4$

		1	2	3	4
$D_e =$	1	0	1	2	1
	2	1	0	1	2
	3	2	1	0	1
	4	1	2	1	0
		4	4	4	4

Calculated S_z and W for graphs G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_4 are presented in Table 5.

Table 2. Distance matrix for $n = 6$

		1	2	3	4	5	6
$D_e =$	1	0	1	2	3	2	1
	2	1	0	1	2	3	2
	3	2	1	0	1	2	3
	4	3	2	1	0	1	2
	5	2	3	2	1	0	1
	6	1	2	3	2	1	0
		9	9	9	9	9	9

Table 3. Distance matrix for $n = 8$

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
$D_e =$	1	0	1	2	3	4	3	2	1
	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	3	2
	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	3
	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4
	5	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3
	6	3	4	3	2	1	0	1	2
	7	2	3	4	3	2	1	0	1
	8	1	2	3	4	3	2	1	0
		16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16

Table 4. Distance matrix for $n = 12$

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
$D_e =$	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	5	4	3	2	1
	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	5	4	3	2
	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	5	4	3
	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	5	4
	5	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	5
	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	5
	8	5	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4
	9	4	5	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3
	10	3	4	5	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	1	2
	11	2	3	4	5	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	1
	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
		36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36

Table 5. Computed values of S_z and W from distance matrices

Graph	Vertices (n)	Column	S_z	$W (= \frac{1}{2} S_z)$
G_1	4	$4 \times 4 = 16$	16	8
G_2	6	$6 \times 9 = 54$	54	27
G_3	8	$8 \times 16 = 128$	128	64
G_4	12	$12 \times 36 = 432$	432	216

From the symmetry of distance matrices of monocyclic graphs a general representation for the computation of S_z

Table 6. Computed values of S_z and W from eq. (2)

Sl. no.	n	m	$S_z = nm^2$	$W = \frac{1}{2} S_z$
1	4	2	16	8
2	6	3	54	27
3	8	4	128	64
4	10	5	250	125
5	12	6	432	216
6	14	7	686	343
7	16	8	1024	512
8	18	9	1458	729
9	20	10	2000	1000

may be taken as

$$S_z = nm^2 \quad (2)$$

where, n even ≥ 4 and $m \in I$, and

$$I = \{m : m \text{ is a positive integer and } m \geq 2\}$$

Then W can be computed from S_z by the relation $W = \frac{1}{2} S_z$. Using eq. (2), the computed S_z and W are presented in Table 6.

Conclusion

The findings S_z and W are obviously in good agreement with the results computed by Khadikar *et al.*⁶ which establishes another procedure for computation of S_z and W . These show that eq. (2) is amenable for computation of S_z and W for monocyclic graphs of n vertices ($n = \text{even} \geq 4$) whatever the distance matrices as shown earlier⁶.

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